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The data for this study is limited to British journals and the research focus is on the main points regarding the subject of “workplace” during 2020. This study is based on two main research questions:

1. Did Covid-19 become a regular topic regarding “workplace” issues each month in British journals in 2020?
2. What were the main insights related to the “workplace” subject in British journals in 2020 and in which frequency?

The methods for this study are compiled with the focus on 102 articles about the workplace from different online journals in Europe listed in Europe News Sources in WorldDataAi. It focuses on thirty-one articles in journals that are published in the United Kingdom. It also makes use of a text mining process on the web-based qualitative analysis tool “3rdeyeinformation”.



For a more in-depth and intuitive analysis of the texts, R studio was used.



Finally, although the articles highlight current issues in the workplace, we have not seen any keywords, which represent change, or actions, which will be taken to address the challenges in workplaces.